

The Gendered Effects of Investing in Physical and Social Infrastructure

Sarah F. Small, University of Utah¹

Yana van der Meulen Rodgers, Rutgers University

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Abstract: Poor infrastructure practices that do not reflect principles of inclusiveness can create real barriers for women which prevent them from effectively participating in the economy. In light of these challenges, we provide a narrative review of studies on the gendered effects of physical and social infrastructure development. We provide a critical analysis of the methodologies commonly used in such studies, and we integrate analysis of strengths and weaknesses of each method in the context of measuring women’s empowerment. We conclude with implications for policy and needs for future research. Ultimately, incorporating gender dimensions into infrastructure planning matters not only for individual well-being but also for promoting overall inclusive and sustainable development.

Highlights:

- We offer a systematic Development Review of gendered dimensions of investment in physical and social infrastructure
- Improvements in physical and social infrastructure strengthen multiple measures of women’s empowerment and gender equality
- Regression analysis dominates research on gender and infrastructure but qualitative and mixed-method studies are necessary
- Women’s participation in infrastructure planning, design, and execution contributes to their empowerment and improved service delivery

Keywords: infrastructure; gender equality; women; economic empowerment; time use; sustainable development; electrification; water and sanitation; transportation; childcare

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I. Introduction

A growing body of knowledge supports the argument that gender equality is necessary for successful and sustainable development (Berik et al. 2009). Yet poor infrastructure practices that do not reflect principles of inclusiveness can create real barriers for women, and barriers that prevent women from effectively participating in the economy and being otherwise empowered, which will result in suboptimal economic and social outcomes. Adequate and gender-responsive infrastructure encourages empowerment: it enables women to work, helps girls stay in school, and frees up women's time. Safe infrastructure allows women to choose schools or workplaces not based on the relative safety of the relevant transportation route but based on the earning potential and quality of work they offer. Infrastructure designed with women in mind also decreases the amount of time women spend on household chores, such as fetching water or collecting firewood, and can in turn improve their paid labor opportunities or time spent in leisure.

Ensuring that countries have gender-responsive infrastructure requires a better understanding of the impact that infrastructure can have on improving the empowerment and socioeconomic status of women. It also requires clear knowledge of how to measure these impacts and how to assess the extent to which infrastructure projects are gender-aware. Hence, this Development Review examines how various forms of infrastructure affect gender equality and women's empowerment, with a focus on the methodologies and measurements used to assess gender outcomes. The review should provide a better understanding of the ways infrastructure development can affect women's equality of opportunity and economic empowerment and how researchers might contribute to this body of work in the future. To our

knowledge this is the first comprehensive review of scholarly studies on the gendered effects of physical and social infrastructure investments.²

We frame our review around a definition of infrastructure which highlights the need for the activation or mobilization of people's freedoms and market potential, and which includes both social and physical infrastructures. For instance, Buhr (2003:19) writes that infrastructure "has the function of rendering possible the opening and development of the economic agents' activities. It puts into action the potentialities of economic units for the benefit of society." With this definition in mind, we select seven categories of infrastructure along both physical and social dimensions. Four of these categories are in physical infrastructure, which is commonly conceptualized as 'hard' engineering works: electricity and energy access, water and sanitation, transportation, and information and communication technology (ICT). The other three categories are in social infrastructure, which is often regarded as the 'poor cousin of physical infrastructure' (Whitzman 2001: 60). We focus on education, healthcare, and social care services as social infrastructures, which is similar to classifications used elsewhere (e.g. Oyvat and Onaran 2022; Ilkkaracan et al. 2021).

How do scholars measure women's equality and empowerment? There is no one-size-fits-all definition of women's empowerment: it can be experienced on several different axes, including socio-cultural, environmental, political, and economic. Kabeer (1999) offers a definition of empowerment as "the process by which those who have been denied the ability to make strategic life choices acquire such an ability," and suggests measuring empowerment along

² As part of their gender-based OLG model, Agénor and Agénor (2023) review literature on relationships between time use and access to physical infrastructure (including transportation, water and sanitation, and electricity). In our review, we are focused not only on time-use, but gendered empowerment broadly, which also includes measures of health, employment, well-being, decision making power, safety, and leisure. We also consider additional physical infrastructures (namely ICT) as well as social infrastructures.

three dimensions: resources, agency, and achievement. Others have defined empowerment as the ability of people to control their own destinies in relation to other people in society (e.g. Mason 2005).

Gender equality, in terms of social and economic rights and opportunities, is often easier to measure compared to overall empowerment. For instance, some scholars measure economic equality through quantitative metrics like wage gaps, labor force participation, employment status, occupational segregation indices, and time-use. However, Sen (1999) and Nussbaum (2003) in their ‘capabilities approach’ framework, encourage scholars to think outside of typical quantitative economic measures and rather focus on empowerment as individuals’ freedoms and capabilities. Indeed, empowerment has been notoriously difficult to measure, as its definition necessitates an understanding of power relations and agency in addition to outcomes commonly observed in studies on gender equality.

The next two sections focus on studies which speak to the ways physical and social infrastructure are related to women’s empowerment, as measured through a variety of channels including time use, paid labor force opportunities, health, and safety. Our discussion of time use includes women’s leisure time: leisure is an important measure of empowerment, and some have argued improvements in women’s leisure time is a central issue to feminist liberation (Henderson 1986).³ In this review we take particular note of the methodologies used to assess gender inclusion impacts and relative effectiveness. We conclude with a discussion of policy implications and an assessment of methodological trends, an overview of gaps in the scholarly literature, and suggestions for research needs going forward.

³ In this review, we do not directly focus on demand-side conditions that affect women's autonomy and economic freedom in developing economies. For example, we do not speak directly to gender differences in job search decisions (Le Barbanchon et al. 2021; Barsoum 2019) or other labor market inequities (Bhalotra et al. 2018) that sprout as a result of broader macro socioeconomic conditions.

II. The Gendered Effects of Physical Infrastructure Development

A key determinant of the constraints that women face in low-income countries is poor physical infrastructure. Policies that would save time by reducing unpaid domestic work and care work include infrastructure improvement to provide water access, electrification, road construction, better transportation options, and sanitation services.⁴ These needs are especially stark in rural areas (Fontana and Elson 2014). One of the biggest determinants of women's time in unpaid labor in low-income countries is the state of public infrastructure including roads and electrification, and ease of access to drinking water and firewood. These areas are usually the domain of women, many of whom have commensurately less time to work for pay given the time-intensive nature of water and firewood collection. In this section, we examine the extent to which the development of physical infrastructure has the potential to improve gender equality and women's opportunities. The studies are concisely summarized in tables in Appendix 1.

A. Electricity and Energy

Improvements in electricity and energy access have generally been shown to improve gender equality by reducing women's time spend on domestic work. Cecelski (2005) uses the Gender Development Index (GDI) and Gender Empowerment Measure (GEM) to explore whether energy consumption is related to gender equity and empowerment. The findings indicate that per capita energy consumption correlates closely with the GDI. The relationship is concave, suggesting that even slight increases in energy and electricity consumption could be associated with substantial improvements in gender-related development in terms of women's life

⁴ We define unpaid domestic work and unpaid labor as socially reproductive activities which are not remunerated through pay. These often include work women do in households like sewing clothes, washing dishes, and preparing meals. Bhattacharya (2017) describes socially reproductive activities in more detail.

expectancy, literacy, and school enrollment. However, Cecelski's (2005) model does not necessarily reflect causal relationships and speaks more broadly to general global trends.

Several studies examining the microeconomic consequences of electrification on women's welfare have found that electrification increases women's labor force participation and empowerment in countries like India, Nicaragua, and South Africa (Rathi and Vermaak 2018; Samad and Zhang 2019; Sedai et al. 2021a; Dinkelman 2011; Grogan and Sadanand 2013). In South Africa, the widescale roll-out of electricity to rural areas resulted in a 9 to 9.5 percentage point increase in women's employment, mostly because household electrification served as a labor-saving technology (largely through electric lighting and cooking) and reduced women's time spent in home production (Dinkelman 2011). However, some studies have found that women spend more time on home production after electrification. Data collected from time use diaries in Peru indicate that electrification of rural areas led to an increase in men's leisure time in the evenings while women spent more time sewing and knitting (Fernández-Baldor et al. 2014).

Sedai et al. (2021b) also examine indirect employment effects resulting from electrification. Using a balanced sample of households from the Indian Human Development Survey, the authors carry out panel fixed effects and instrumental variable regressions to estimate the effect of electricity reliability on household work hours, employment, health, and intrahousehold decision-making outcomes. They find that reliable electrification improves the status of women in India through increased employment opportunities and reduced time allocation to home production. Namely, they find that 10 more hours of access to home electricity increases the likelihood of employment by 2.8 percentage points for men and 4.2 percentage points for women. One of the mediating factors is the reduced time burden of labor-

intensive activities like fuel and water collection as a result of electrification. The authors also find that electrification improves women's general health and increases their say in economic decisions, mobility, and reproductive choices.

One important distinction in this study lies in the measurement of electrification. Many studies have used a simple binary measure of electrification, indicating whether or not a household has any access. However, as Sedai et al. (2021a), Sedai et al. (2021b), and Harish et al. (2014) point out, this binary metric of whether people have/do not have an electricity connection can be very misleading. Lack of supply reliability, especially during peak periods, acts as an impediment to post-electrification decisions, such as the purchase of domestic appliances (such as a fridge, computer, washing machine, and heater), which lowers the required time for home production, and it restricts the efficient allocation of women's time in home production and paid labor (Ferrant and Thim 2019). The authors, therefore, make use non-binary count measures to capture adequate access to electricity. One such measurement is based on responses from the Indian Human Development Survey capturing the typical number of hours per day a household generally has power. They supplement this measure with controls for typical voltage by region using India's Ministry of Power data.

Still, many of the other studies which use bimodal measures of electrification provide insightful findings. For instance, Samad and Zhang (2019) conduct a cross-sectional analysis of women's empowerment using the spatial variation in access to electrification. Their results show that access to electricity increases not only women's employment, but also their freedom of movement (such as their ability to visit various places, including health centers and friends' or relatives' homes, and to travel a short distance by trains or buses) and social participation (namely, awareness of socio-political issues and membership in social groups).

In addition to these indirect improvements in women's employment, improved energy infrastructure also poses opportunities to directly improve women's employment. More specifically, energy infrastructure projects which include women in management and production roles can improve both the design of the infrastructure and women's overall employment. Using nationally representative data, research from Kazakhstan indicates that women's representation among energy-sector managers has been falling over time, and this was worsened by COVID-19 and childcare deficits (Atakhanova and Howie 2022). Lessons from this research point to the importance of addressing education and childcare infrastructure needs in efforts to recruit and retain women managers in energy infrastructure projects.

Analyses of electrification and gender empowerment are not limited to quantitative studies. For example, Kim and Standal (2019) consider access to electrification in terms of reliability in a qualitative study in rural Kyrgyzstan. Their findings suggest that lack of reliability and affordability of electricity in rural areas has undermined women's potential empowerment and has worked to maintain gender inequalities. They determine that because women are relied upon to maintain heating in frigid, mountainous homes during frequent electricity blackouts instead of having the home heated through electricity, their time is constrained by activities such as collecting firewood and cooking. This often keeps women in the home where they otherwise might have been able to focus on other responsibilities or take on new employment opportunities. Extreme heat is also a problem, as exemplified in Garg et al.'s (2020) study on China showing that in homes without air conditioning and other cooling technologies, extreme heat contributes to reduced time spent on farm work and on childcare, especially for women. As episodes of extreme heat become more common with climate change, such technologies will become increasingly important.

Other studies suggest that the mode of delivery of energy products matters in gender equality. For example, Standal and Winther (2016) have two ethnographic case studies in rural communities in Uttar Pradesh, India, and Bamiyan, Afghanistan. They find that electrification provided important resources and enhanced women's opportunities to perform their expected role as care workers more efficiently, and that many women appreciated this positive effect of electricity in their everyday lives. However, in Uttar Pradesh, electricity reinforced structures of gender inequality. This finding is attributed to the widespread belief that women are primarily end-users in the energy sector and are generally not included in the process and politics of forming new energy solutions. In contrast, there are signs that women's status increased in the Bamiyan case, which the authors link to the atypical inclusion and training of women as solar engineers in the electricity supply. This study suggests the importance of implementation strategies: how can communities introduce electrification in ways that also introduce new visions of gender equality? In the case of Bamiyan, it was through the mainstreaming and normalization of women engineers.

As many regions take on new, greener forms of energy production, there are certainly opportunities to consider how gender dynamics can be improved through their introduction. Osunmuyiwa and Ahlborg (2022) suggest that relying on new energy and power structures has the potential to disrupt community gender hierarchies but can fall short. They examine this dynamic in terms of women's entrepreneurship in Tanzania, and they find through qualitative interviews and focus groups that the introduction of small-scale renewable energy systems meant that women entrepreneurs had more opportunities to expand their businesses. In addition, the new systems gave them more room to maneuver in daily life, and some shifts in gender norms followed. However, women had a more difficult time accessing credit needed to obtain small-

scale renewable energy systems, which the authors suggest ought to be considered when introducing such technologies.

B. Water and Sanitation

Like electrification, infrastructures promoting access to clean water have been shown to improve numerous outcomes for women in several regions. For example, household survey data show that in rural communities in the Philippines, Uganda, and Zimbabwe, access to an improved water source reduced women's average unpaid care workloads by one to four hours per day (Rost and Koissy-Kpein 2018). Moreover, in Black Tickle, a remote Inuit community in Labrador, Canada, many indigenous women reported that no piped water and limited access to potable water lengthened their workdays and undermined their physical and mental health (Hanrahan and Mercer 2019). In northern Morocco, Devoto et al. (2012) offer a random subset of homeowners a simplified procedure to purchase a household water grid connection on credit. Among those who took up the access to the water grid, they experienced time gains which were used primarily for leisure and social activities and within six months, overall household well-being improved. However, while the authors find that access to water increased leisure and social activities, employment and earnings were not improved. Still, improvements in leisure can be important aspects of improvements in empowerment. Closely related, evidence from randomized trials in Kenya shows that investments in infrastructure to protect spring water lead to less fecal contamination and a lower incidence of child diarrhea, which helps to reduce the time that women spend in unpaid labor activities (Kremer et al. 2011).

Improvements in water infrastructure can indirectly support women's employment. In India, adult women spend 1–2 hours daily on average collecting and storing water, and studies have shown that time spent on water collection negatively affect both women's employment and

personal health (Fletcher et al. 2017). Sedai (2021) studies the effect of the National Rural Drinking Water Program and indoor piped water on employment and earnings by gender in India. Using the Indian Human Development Survey (2005–2012) and econometric analyses, Sedai (2021) finds that a 0.1% increase in village access to indoor piped drinking water increases the likelihood of women's overall employment by 0.33 percentage points and women's wage/salary employment by 0.39 percentage points. Much of this has to do with the time saved by piped water. Moreover, in India's slum areas, the provision of tap water and sanitation services (along with electrification and paved roads) has contributed to a substantial increase in education for women along with reduced health costs (Parikh et al. 2015).

Closely related, Winter et al. (2021) study the effect of piped water systems installed in rural villages of southern Zambia and finds that households that obtained piped water reduced their fetching time by 80%, with the majority of time saved accruing to women and girls. The authors come to these results through a quasi-experimental study of four villages in rural Zambia. They use a combination of household surveys, Global Positioning System transponders, and water meters to measure time spent fetching water, water consumption, and how water was being used for domestic and productive activities. Access to toilets has also been shown to indirectly improve women's employment and empowerment. Using district-level data from India, results from a two-stage regression analysis indicate that latrine availability in India is positively associated with women's labor force participation and women's literacy rates. The effect is especially strong in rural communities (Gius and Subramanian 2015).

In addition to improvements in earnings and employment among women, Sedai (2021) also finds that indoor piped drinking water improves health outcomes among women in India. This finding contributes to a body of research that associates the lack of access to clean water in

households with an increase in short-term morbidities (such as fever, cough, and diarrhea) and the inability to reallocate domestic chores that prevent children from attending school (Koolwal and Van de Walle 2013). Water and sanitation access is also associated with improved birth weights (Baker et al. 2018) The time that is freed up when women have increased access to clean water can also increase their leisure time, as shown in Meeks (2017) with evidence based on time use data from Kyrgyzstan.

That said, women's improved outcomes from investments in water and sanitation infrastructure are not always so clear. For instance, research in the Shivalik Hills of northwest India shows that men's expectations of water use changed when infrastructure interventions brought piped water to the region. Piped water reduced the distance women walked to reach water sources, but there was an increase in the volume of water women were expected to carry (Narain 2014). The author employs a qualitative research design, which relied on semi-structured interviews, direct observation, and participatory rural appraisal tools. Similarly, a study of nationally representative quantitative data in Indonesia finds that households with piped water are more likely to rely on women to fetch additional water compared to those without piped water (Irianti and Prasetyoputra 2019). Another study on Bangalore finds that while many local women acknowledged that piped water might save time and increase mobility, they retorted that the requirement to pay for the water outweighed the benefits of piped water (Thara 2017). Still, the importance of improved water and sanitation infrastructures has become increasingly clear as the climate crisis rages on. A study in the Melamchi watershed area of Nepal finds that a decrease in water volume and changes in the geography of water sources led to increased water stress borne by women (Shrestha et al. 2019).

Water infrastructure projects which include women in the design and development directly improve women's employment and have the potential to improve community access. Were et al. (2008) find that community organization around water supply improved when women were included in having responsibility for water management in the highlands of Western Kenya. Leino (2007), on the other hand, finds no evidence that increases in women's participation in water user committees altered other outcomes in the community, but suggests that gender inclusion in water management can be a useful way to boost women's empowerment without distorting delivery of public goods. Grant et al. (2019) find that women's ownership and management of water supply infrastructures in rural Cambodia led to improvements in women's empowerment, but that they were constrained by domestic obligations.

Leite (2010) sets out some examples of women's employment in water and sanitation programs. For instance, she introduces case studies from a rainwater harvesting project in Brazil where qualitative interviews indicate that women were able to develop water management techniques, gain an income, take on leadership positions, and negotiate for their interests in the public decision-making bodies that handled water supply and sanitation related issues. Leite (2010) also shows that women's participation in water infrastructure projects can reduce rates of mortality and morbidity due to water-borne diseases. She argues that women's participation in decision-making positions in water and sanitation management institutions leads to the possibility of women's empowerment because they are able to control a key resource and have an increased level of confidence.

C. Transportation

Limited transport and transportation infrastructure can exacerbate gender inequality. Women often face more constraints on mobility and travel than men, particularly in low-income

countries. For example, in sub-Saharan Africa, men tend to be the principal operators and owners of commercial motorized and non-motorized transport, while women are commonly pedestrian transporters (Porter 2008). Time use studies have found similar results in South Asian countries such as Pakistan, where men account for about 80% of all trips and are more likely than women to use motorized transportation for these trips (Adeel et al. 2017). Women's constrained transportation options can be problematic. Women frequently travel with dependents and because they have less access to vehicular travel than men, they often walk further and rely upon rudimentary infrastructure such as footpaths and trail bridges to complete household chores (Njenga and Tanzarn, 2020). Because men's and women's mobility, travel mode, and travel purposes differ in meaningful ways, it is important to capture both men's and women's experiences in the decision-making processes that steer transportation infrastructure development.

Transit constraints can mean that women require more travel time, which may exacerbate their time scarcity. For example, time use data from Ghana indicate that traffic congestion in urban areas contributes to time poverty rates that are higher for women than men, with the implication that investment in the public transportation infrastructure can reduce the spent stuck in traffic and help to reduce time poverty (Orkoh et al. 2020). Improvements in transportation infrastructure often come with improvements in women's labor force participation. Using data from the India Human Development Survey, Lei et al. (2019) examine how village transportation infrastructure affects women's and men's employment. Results from their fixed-effect regression analysis show that paved roads, unpaved roads, and frequent bus services increase the odds of non-agricultural employment among both men and women, but the effect is stronger among women. Moreover, census data for India show that in more urban areas, proximity to the Delhi

Metro stations significantly increases the female employment rate, whereas its effect on men's employment is ambiguous (Seki and Yamada 2020).

A study in Lima, Peru comes to similar conclusions about women's employment: Martinez et al. (2020) use national household survey data to quantify the causal impacts of improved urban transport systems on women's employment outcomes, looking at Bus Rapid Transit and elevated light rail investments in the metropolitan region of Lima. They find evidence of increased use of public transit among women and large gains in employment and earnings among women. Additionally, research from Nicaragua based on household survey data shows that new rural trail bridges result in a 60% increase in women entering the labor market (Brooks and Donovan 2020). Many of these findings suggest that infrastructure investments that make it more convenient and safer for women to use public transport can generate important labor market impacts for women.

Improvements in transportation infrastructure are also pivotal to women's health. For example, using a mixed-methods approach incorporating geographic information system analysis and individual data from semi-structured interviews, Ouko et al. (2019) estimate that poor geographic access to healthcare providers is the single biggest contributor to maternal mortality rates in Siaya County, Kenya. Closely related, women who had recently given birth in Uganda and Zambia had average travel times to the nearest health clinic that exceeded an hour, with even longer durations for women in the lowest income groups. For those women who delivered at home, lack of affordability, accessibility, and adequacy in transportation options helped to explain why they did not travel to the health facility (Sacks et al. 2016). However, public transit is not always the solution: in Belgium, women use public transportation more often than men to

travel for work and family reasons, and they were therefore more likely to be exposed to COVID-19 (Assoumou Ella 2021).

Increasing available transportation alone is not enough to ensure that women's well-being is enhanced. In fact, increased transportation infrastructure can add to the amount of traffic and cash that flows through particular areas, and violence and harassment have resulted as unforeseen byproducts (Njenga and Tanzarn, 2020). Additionally, many women risk bodily safety when walking or taking public transit, so new infrastructure needs to prioritize women's safety. Based on interviews with users, the introduction of Delhi Metro is shown to have drastically changed transportation choices for women, due to the high safety standard in the Metro system (Onishi 2017). However, Delhi's Metro is expensive and often inaccessible for lower income residents (Kumar 2008). Still, Borker (2021) provides a novel quantitative study which supports the importance of safety in women's transportation routes. This research is based on a unique dataset that combines information on 4,000 surveyed students at the University of Delhi, maps of potential travel routes to all colleges in the students' choice set using an algorithm developed in Google Maps, and crowd-sourced mobile application safety data. Results indicate that women are willing to choose a college in the bottom half of the quality distribution over a college in the top quintile in order to travel by a safer route. The priority that women place on safety is also reflected in an Australian study based on observational data showing that women commuter cyclists prefer to use routes with maximum separation from motorized traffic while men are more willing to bike closer to traffic (Garrard et al. 2008). The authors suggest that improved cycling infrastructure in the form of bicycle paths and lanes that provide a high degree of separation from motor traffic is important for increasing transportation cycling among women.

In an effort to bolster women's security and improve their mobility in the face of social norms that discourage women from leaving their homes or traveling alone, some countries have begun to implement transportation policies and provide facilities that allow men and women to travel separately (Dinkelman and Ngai 2022). For example, Mexico City's "women traveling safely program," which includes women-only subway cars, has resulted in lower rates of sexual harassment against women riders during the times when this option was available (Aguilar et al. 2021). Closely related, experimental evidence from Rio de Janeiro shows that creating a safe space reserved for women on the suburban rail system reduces the rate of physical harassment by 50% (Kondylis et al. 2020).

In addition to safety considerations, transportation needs to be affordable to women. Salon and Gulyani (2010) surveyed 4,375 low-income residents in Nairobi, Kenya, and found that the majority cannot afford any of the motorized transport options in the city. People cope by limiting their travel outside their settlement and, if they do travel, it is often by walking. They also find that women and children disproportionately bear the burden of reduced mobility. Further, there is growing evidence pointing to the benefits of employing women in rural road maintenance, construction, rehabilitation, management, and planning. Winslott Hiselius et al. (2019) find that women's presence in local policymaking leads to more environmentally sustainable transportation policies. Others have argued that their inclusion is important for the expression of specific needs in infrastructural planning and implementation processes (Kaiser and Barstow 2022).

D. Information and Communication Technology

A growing body of research indicates that women's economic livelihoods are enhanced by improvements in ICT infrastructure (Ibrahim and Adamu 2016). One such dimension is

business ownership. For instance, in a seven-year field quasi-experiment in rural Indian villages, Venkatesh et al. (2017) find that ICT intervention strongly impacts entrepreneurship, with 160 new businesses in the 10 intervention villages compared to 40 in the control villages. The highest levels of entrepreneurial activity are observed among women with high ICT use. Also examining ICT, Crittenden et al. (2019) use structural equation modeling applied to survey data from 199 women micro-entrepreneurs in South Africa and find that that ICT usage decisions among women entrepreneurs were influenced by their perceptions of ease of use and usefulness.

Using qualitative interview methods, Mumporeze and Prieler (2017) research barriers to women's access to ICT in Rwanda. They find that heavy domestic responsibilities and computer anxiety keep women from using ICT at higher rates, and they recommend that Rwandan women have improved access to education in computer technologies. The authors applaud the One Laptop Per Child program for acquainting girls with computers at an early age. Research in the Peruvian context also indicates that improvements in access to ICT have increased women's access to education (Ávila and Abad 2019).

Other scholars have found that ICT infrastructure can improve women's overall independence and freedom. Laizu et al. (2010) use a structured questionnaire to collect data from women in two different villages in Bangladesh where ICT projects have been introduced. The authors compare changes in women's perception after using ICT to changes in women who did not use ICT. They find that in one of the villages, women who used ICT had a higher sense of independence, freedom, and self-esteem. However, this was not the case in the second village. The difference may be due to domestic control of ICT resources. Handapangoda and Kumara's (2013) work – based on ethnographic surveys of 30 unemployed housewives from poor households – shows that when women had access to mobile phones, it strengthened and

expanded their social circle and support networks and opened them up to newer activities, a manifestation of choice and power. However, the authors find that these effects were dampened when the phones were controlled by their husbands.

The spread of ICT services has also facilitated innovations in financial technology, mobile financial services, and mobile money, which have helped to promote poverty reduction and income redistribution in a number of countries (Suri and Jack 2016). More broadly, access to and participation in well-functioning financial infrastructures are also pivotal in women's empowerment. Much has been written in development economics on the gendered effects of microloans, so we leave reviews of such works to other scholars (e.g. Armendáriz and Morduch 2010; Khan and Khan 2016). We do, however, note a few studies related to credit and women's entrepreneurship. In particular, Asiedu et al. (2013) find that female-owned firms are more credit constrained in sub-Saharan Africa than male-owned. However, Menon and Rodgers (2011) find that in India, access to credit encourages women's self-employment, which may be an avenue to women's empowerment. Similarly, Nwosu and Orji's (2017) work shows that access to formal credit improves women entrepreneur's likelihood of successful enterprise performance, and therefore their ability to earn money.

In a study of 98 developing countries, Demirgüç-Kunt et al. (2013) find women's access to banking is closely related to country-level restrictions on women's work, violence against women, and early age marriage. Another cross-country study finds that women are more likely to be excluded from the financial sector in countries where credit information is less available through public and private credit registries and where gaps between women and men in educational attainment are large (Morsy 2020). Some improvements in financial access have come with access to mobile banking, but studies in Pakistan (Glavee-Geo et al. 2017) and

Singapore (Riquelme and Rios 2010) find that women are especially sensitive to social norms around banking and finance, which affects their likelihood of using mobile banking services.

Unbanked women may rely more on community networks and informal borrowing to finance their spending. This assertion is supported by Tsai's (2000) work on South China, which finds women often make use of rotating savings and credit associations (ROSCAs) to fill the gap in financing needs. Anderson and Baland (2002) examine the use of ROSCAs in Kenya and find most women use ROSCAs to protect their savings against claims made by their husbands for immediate consumption. Sedai et al. (2021c) find that women's ROSCA membership in India improves their decision-making power in households as well as their fertility choice making. While ROSCAs have proven to be helpful for many women, Chen et al. (2017) find that, in China, many women are disproportionately penalized in peer-to-peer lending platforms: the authors find that female borrowers pay higher interest rates even though default rates of loans from female borrowers are significantly lower than those from male borrowers. Ultimately, banking and finance infrastructures may improve women's pathways to empowerment, but such infrastructures need to consider equal access and opportunity to credit in their design.

Of course, digital and cellular technology can also prolong working hours, both paid and unpaid, so the spread of ICT services is not a sufficient condition to reduce women's time constraints and improve their economic empowerment. To the extent that income gains enable women to reallocate their unpaid domestic work to others in the home or to purchase market substitutes, these advances in ICT should contribute to greater gender equality. There are other important caveats to the beneficial effects of ICT for women's empowerment. For instance, Western Kenya has experienced improvements in ICT, but women often have poor access (Wyche and Olson 2018). Through observations of and group interviews with women mobile

phone owners, the authors find that women tend to have secondhand cell phones which are often broken, face heavy time constraints of unpaid work, and face misinformation about social media which inhibits their ability to effectively use ICT. Similarly, Primo and Khan (2003) note that men are free to walk long distances (during the day or night) to seek Internet cafes, while women must focus on home chores or are unable to walk at night. Others have found that women's access to ICT have been prohibited by costs (e.g. Gillwald et al. 2010). For these reasons, gender inequities in access to and usage of ICTs may not be entirely addressed through ICT infrastructure development per se. Greater inclusion of women in occupations which rely on technology will help to improve their access to and knowledge of ICT.

III. The Gendered Effects of Social Infrastructure

Policies that boost women's employment are less effective in improving their well-being if they do not reduce women's time spent performing unpaid domestic labor. A crucial way to do so is to strengthen social infrastructure, especially through the provision of affordable care services. Deficits in social infrastructure – especially insufficient access to affordable schooling, healthcare, and care services – are a key determinant of the constraints that women face in their own empowerment. This issue has gained increasing attention during the Covid-19 pandemic as the need for childcare provision, homeschooling, and healthcare rose dramatically when schools closed and people became sick. In this section, we examine the extent to which the development of social infrastructure has the potential to improve gender equality and women's opportunities, with a focus on education, healthcare, and social care services. The studies are also concisely summarized in tables in Appendix 2. The evidence indicates that investing in social infrastructure can grow employment in ways that reduce unpaid work burdens, meet basic needs, and reallocate women's time from unpaid to remunerated work.

A. Education

Women and girls' education in itself has been lauded as an outcome of empowerment. However, improving educational infrastructures and access to education has the potential to spark lasting benefits that contribute to gender equality and empowerment. For example, several studies have found that increasing women's access to education has the potential to improve their decision-making ability about fertility. Chicoine's (2021) quantitative study examined how the removal of school fees led to an increase in schooling for Ethiopian women, and that each additional year of schooling led to a reduction in fertility. This study also finds that this corresponding decline in fertility is associated with an increase in labor market opportunities. These conclusions are drawn from a difference-in-differences model using data from the Ethiopian census and from three rounds of the Demographic and Health Survey (DHS). The increase in schooling is identified by combining the timing of the removal of fees and geographic variation in schooling outcomes for cohorts who completed their education before the introduction of the schooling reform. Similar methods and results are found in work by Zenebe Gebre (2019), who use a difference-in-differences model to study how the introduction of free primary education in Malawi led to reductions in fertility. The author suggests the program improved women's abilities to postpone marriage, delay first births, and use contraceptives. Similarly, a study using Indonesian DHS data and multivariate logistic regression models finds that a woman's sense of confidence in asking her husband to use a condom improved with higher levels of education (Putra et al. 2021).

Another group of studies have examined the links between women's education and domestic violence. For example, Eze-Ajoku et al. (2022) use Nigeria's DHS data to show that women with higher levels of education are less tolerant of spousal physical violence. However,

some studies have found that women's increased empowerment, especially in terms of higher levels of education, can trigger a backlash effect among men, sometimes putting women at even higher risks of domestic violence (Hosein 2019).

In addition to these aforementioned health outcomes, improved access to education can improve women's earning potential, which helps reduce gendered economic inequities and, in some cases, may improve women's intrahousehold bargaining power. Such evidence is found in Bangladesh (Hossain and Tisdell 2005), Pakistan (Shah 2007), and other regions (Le and Nguyen 2021). However, some caveats remain. For instance, in India, women's education and labor force participation have a U-shaped relationship. Part of the decline at moderate levels of education may be due to an income effect, where women with more education marry into richer families that enable them to withdraw from the labor force. Using two waves of the India Human Development Survey, Chatterjee et al. (2018) regress a measure of labor force participation on education levels for married women. The authors find that the income effect accounts for some of the U-shape, but not all, and suggest that a lack of suitable employment opportunities for moderately educated women is also to blame.

Though improving women's access to education has generally positive effects on gender equality and empowerment, several barriers persist. Using both qualitative and quantitative data, Ojobo (2008) finds that economic constraints, religious constraints, unpaid domestic responsibilities, unequal employment opportunities, and early marriage are largely responsible for gender differences in educational attainment in Nigeria. A similar cautionary point is made in Jacoby and Mansuri (2011), with the argument that the optimal placement of new schools needs to take into account social restrictions on mobility that girls may face, particularly in South Asian countries. Other research has found that recruiting and retaining female teachers is effective at

reducing gender gaps in rural children's education, which they measure through regionally reported student test scores (Muralidharan and Sheth 2016). What are some of the lessons here? Women need to be included in education policy reforms in order to surpass some of these barriers, and the stereotypical sexual division of labor needs to be discarded, which may be helped along by improvements in childcare infrastructure (Ojobo 2008).

B. Healthcare

Access to adequate healthcare infrastructure has the potential to improve women's empowerment. Medical services which allow women to control their fertility and to care for their bodies are empowering in themselves, but also allow them better opportunities to participate in paid work. In other words, women's access to reproductive, non-reproductive, and mental healthcare are all pivotal in their wellbeing. For instance, Osundina (2020) finds a positive relationship between the health status of women in Nigeria and their labor force participation. However, some infrastructure challenges keep women from accessing the care they need. Work by Sreenu (2019) uses primary quantitative and qualitative surveys to identify challenges faced by public rural Indian healthcare facilities. The data indicate that many of the facilities are in poor condition, that there is a limited supply of healthcare workers, and that due to geographic constraints, many community members turn to more expensive, private care to meet their needs. Similarly, in several countries across sub-Saharan Africa and southeast Asia, qualitative interviews indicate that young women who want contraceptives and healthcare often cannot get these services because of the long distance (Williamson et al. 2009). Others have found that war negatively affect women's access to reproductive care due to war-related transportation and infrastructure changes and as well as other health services taking priority (Hedström & Herder 2023).

In addition to transportation to healthcare, ICT for healthcare providers can also improve health outcomes for women. In a study in rural Indonesia, mobile phones were introduced to midwives. Findings from qualitative interviews with the midwives indicate that the mobile phones helped facilitate smoother communication and allowed speedier emergency response. The phones also helped them gather and disseminate health-related information to the patient community (Chib 2010).

Finally, even when individuals are able to reach a hospital, the facility's accessibility can be poor and inhibit usage. In a qualitative study on maternal health access for women with disabilities in Ghana, several women, particularly those suffering physical and visual impairments, reported that most healthcare facilities currently lack ramps, wheelchairs, and disability-friendly delivery beds. These problems often overlapped with one another and with communication problems, which discouraged some women from seeking healthcare from skilled providers (Ganle et al. 2016).

C. Social Care Services

Women's disproportionate responsibility in performing care work is an issue that has garnered long-term attention in the field of development economics, with valuable lessons for understanding how women are impacted by increased access to social infrastructure and care services. Numerous scholars have examined the role of unpaid care work as a barrier to women's empowerment (e.g. Sinha and Sedai 2022; Folbre 2014), so improving care infrastructures offers opportunities for sustainable improvements in women's well-being. Much of women's care work is focused on children, but women also take care of elderly, sick, and disabled family members. Hence the relevant care infrastructure includes provision of paid family leave and paid sick

leave, universal free/affordable childcare and long-term eldercare, and improved terms of employment for paid care workers.

Studies from around the world have indicated that access to childcare improves women's ability to participate more fully in the economy. For instance, Kawabata (2014) finds that access to childcare is closely associated with a higher probability of attaining preferred employment among women with preschool-aged children in Tokyo. The author uses geospatial data on care centers and their capacity, paired with survey data from an Internet-based questionnaire on work and childcare with answers from 311 mothers in Tokyo. Studies on South American cities find similar conclusions. For instance, Barros et al. (2013) examine the impact of access to childcare on women's labor market outcomes in Rio de Janeiro. Employing a lottery system for free publicly-provided childcare in low-income neighborhoods, the authors use a randomized control trial to find that access to free publicly provided child care leads to a large increase in the use of care, a considerable increase in mothers' employment, and an almost doubling in the employment of mothers who were not working before the lottery took place. They also find that the rise in mothers' employment is associated with a 16% increase in household incomes. A similar study on Guatemala City analyzes the labor force participation and hours worked of mothers in urban slums using survey data of 1,300 mothers with preschool children. The survey was designed and collected as part of an impact evaluation of the 'Hogares Comunitarios' government-sponsored, home-based day care program. The authors use simulations to illustrate that reductions in care prices and in travel time to care providers have a large positive effect on low-income women's labor hours (Hallman et al. 2005).

Research from another randomized control trial in Nairobi indicates that limited access to affordable early childcare inhibits poor women's participation in paid work (Clark et al. 2019).

More specifically, the study finds that women who were offered vouchers for subsidized childcare were 8.5 percentage points more likely to be employed than those who were not given vouchers. Most of these employment gains were realized by married mothers, but single mothers benefited by shifting to jobs with more regular hours. The study also finds that access to subsidized daycare increased women's participation in decisions around children's healthcare. However, women's participation in decision making on household finances and purchases were not shown to be improved as a result of the vouchers (Clark et al. 2019).

Despite many of the benefits that women accrue from childcare provision, several obstacles remain. Moussié (2021) documents major barriers to childcare for women informal workers in cities and assesses the role that municipalities can play in the provision of childcare services. Women informal workers may not qualify for means-tested safety net programs like childcare subsidies, and as a result, their livelihoods and their children suffer. Moussié (2021) highlights locational challenges, as childcare centers are often not near areas where informal workers work (such as in a marketplace or near a waste dump or recycling plant).

In terms of eldercare, the caring labor of adult children plays an important role in meeting the health needs of elderly adults, and a similar argument holds for the care of sick and disabled family members. While lower-income and middle-income countries still have relatively young populations, projections show their demographic transitions are progressing rapidly with considerable shifts in the population age structures toward the elderly. These shifts have already prompted legislative reforms to build and reinforce the social safety net to better support older persons, but progress has remained uneven depending on the size of public sector health budgets (Mahal and McPake 2017; Rodgers and Zveglic 2021). In the meantime informal care from another adult in the home acts as a substitute for care from a professional provider, with families

using their own unpaid labor, especially that of women, to provide care for older family members (Stark 2005). Unpaid care for older men is often provided by spouses, while for women it is provided by other family members, especially by daughters, as documented for Korea (Yoon 2014), China (Chen et al. 2018), and Western Europe (Stark and Cukrowska-Torzewska 2018). The mechanisms through which childcare services alleviate the constraints that women face in their labor market attachment are comparable to the ways in which greater social support for eldercare and care of the sick can free women's time to engage more time in paid work, other household activities, and leisure.

IV. Main Takeaways and Knowledge Gaps

At first blush, the literature on gendered effects of infrastructure investment appears to be broad in regional scope, rigorous in methodologies, and comprehensive in types of infrastructure analyzed. Yet there are knowledge gaps that need to be filled with new research. In addition to policy recommendations, which we discuss in Section V, what can be gleaned from this Development Review? We offer several suggestions to researchers related to research methods and knowledge gaps.

A. Improved Data Collection & Moving Away from Unitary Household Models

The way in which gender is analyzed often boils down to data availability. Data on employment rates by (typically binary measures of) gender is readily available, which helps to explain why empirical studies on infrastructure and gender often use labor force statistics to capture the gender dimension. We contend that greater efforts are needed to measure women's economic empowerment through the lens of resources, agency, and achievement – a la Kabeer (1999) – when researching infrastructure impacts.

Closely related, conceptual issues have also played a role in limiting our knowledge of who within households is actually benefitting from or getting access to infrastructure improvements. With much research implicitly or explicitly being set in the context of a unitary household model, not only was income assumed to be distributed evenly within households, but so was the allocation of household work. The implication was then that everyone in the household benefits equally from infrastructure investment. However, the unitary household model has since encountered much resistance, largely by scholars examining power differentials within the household (e.g. Agarwal 1997). It has become clear that gender differences in the allocation of unpaid work within the household are a key determinant of intra-household inequalities by gender in access to time for paid work; ultimately, this uneven intrahousehold allocation of labor manifests as observed gender differences in income and time poverty. More research is needed on how new infrastructure influences these intrahousehold dynamics, and how intrahousehold dynamics are determining who within the household is gaining from infrastructure improvements.

B. Research Methods: Quantitative, Qualitative, or Mixed Method?

Throughout this review, we reference studies which capture these dimensions of women's economic empowerment and gender equality in several different ways, including regression analysis with large-scale survey data, case studies, randomized control trials, time-use diaries, qualitative interviews, ethnographies, and mixed methods. Some scholars have strong preferences for the methods by which empowerment metrics are calculated. The conventional practice among economists is to use an econometric method applied to data that are mostly generated by census or survey questionnaires with pre-coded categories, and are most frequently collected and processed by others, often national governments or statistical agencies.

Despite the dominance of regression analysis based on large-scale survey datasets in the economics profession, this methodology cannot identify country-specific factors that may influence outcomes. There is growing recognition, especially among feminist researchers, that regression analyses should be coupled with local case studies or qualitative methods to determine the context that underlies the association between dependent variables and structural forces (Beetham and Demetriades 2007; Hesse-Biber 2012; Garcia and Ramirez 2021). Exceptional cases are also sources of insight in helping countries determine policies that they could either adapt or avoid. Indeed, Busse and Nunnenkamp (2009) identify country case studies as a useful methodology to sort out questions about the unobservable transmission mechanisms between gender educational equality and foreign direct investment. This move toward methodological complementarity is consistent with feminist economists' interest in understanding process and agency as well as outcomes (Berik et al. 2009).

Over the last two decades, randomized controlled trials have gained a “gold standard” reputation in empirical microeconomics and in development economics. Many researchers view them as impartial and necessary to establish casual relationships in empirical investigations. But influential as randomized controlled trials have been, their criticisms also continue apace (Donovan 2018). Many are related to their small scale, limited temporal extent, external and even internal validity, costs of implementation, ethical oversights, and technocratic orientation (Rodgers et al. 2020). Further, some critique quantitative measures of expected empowerment outcomes (such as paid employment) because these outcomes are not always achieved through women's empowerment, but often through difficult circumstance that limits women's choices (Mason 2005).

In response to these critiques, some scholars have turned to time use diaries to measure women's empowerment and gender gaps in social indicators of development. Time use data typically come from two sources: stand-alone time use surveys, and modular time use surveys that are part of a major national effort such as a labor force survey or household income and expenditure survey (Hirway 2010). Regardless of the source, the researcher typically has access to three data components: (1) background and socioeconomic information about the individual and/or household; (2) time spent by individuals on different types of activities, usually in the past 24 hours or in the past week; and (3) the context in which the person engages in the activities, such as where the activities took place, who else was present, and whether or not the activity was paid. The inclusion of these metrics helps to provide the richer context that is often missing in studies based on regression analysis or randomized control trials.

Given a well-performed survey, time use surveys might actually be the best way to understand the relationship between infrastructure access and women's time use, and particularly how that relationship can vary with socioeconomic status, religion, caste, and location. For example, the relationship between social infrastructure and time spent on informal eldercare in the home depends partly on the opportunity cost of one's time, which depends on socioeconomic status as well as the activities that are foregone as a result of providing this care. Time use surveys can be a useful tool for measuring this opportunity cost, as in Chari et al. (2015). As another example of context, women are likely to have higher time poverty rates than men in low-income countries in sub-Saharan Africa with poor physical infrastructure, while this gender gap in time poverty is ameliorated and sometimes even reversed in middle-income and higher-income countries in the Middle East and North Africa with social norms that restrict women's engagement in paid employment. Similarly, women may be constrained by caste-based status

restrictions in which married women are discouraged from participating in the labor market. Data from time use surveys in India substantiate such constraints and show that women reallocated their time away from market work toward activities such as childcare and networking that reinforced their social status (Eswaran et al. 2013).

As of 2020, over 100 countries had conducted at least one time use survey, with more expected to come on board (Floro 2021). Unfortunately, time use surveys vary considerably in what gets measured and how they measure it, so types of activities are not consistent in definition or aggregation across countries. This lack of consistency makes it difficult to compare time use statistics across countries with a single time-use activity classification, which would be necessary if one wants to have a uniform measure of something like time poverty or economic empowerment across countries. Although there is an International Classification of Activities for Time Use Studies (ICATUS), countries don't necessarily abide or follow this scheme (Hirway 2010; Floro 2021). One way to overcome this obstacle and perform cross-country comparisons is to use a harmonization process that converts the time use data into a standardized format. Following this approach, Rubiano-Matulevich and Viollaz (2019) find that women perform less market work and substantially more unpaid domestic work than men in a sample of 19 countries across different regions. Harmonized time use surveys are readily available for European countries through the Eurostat online portal but are less common for lower-income countries. Another way to improve the usefulness of time use surveys is to conduct more longitudinal time use surveys that allow researchers to control for fixed unobserved heterogeneity when examining changes over time, such as Miller and Sedai's (2022) examination of the trade-off between caregiving and time devoted to other activities, including paid work and leisure.

Qualitative, observational studies are often lauded as those which capture empowerment most effectively, in that researchers can more concretely observe the triangulation of women's resources, agency, and achievement. However, gathering information along all these dimensions can be time consuming, and researchers cannot always cover enough households or communities to aggregate their analyses (Mason 2005). We contend that mixed-methods approaches, those using both qualitative and quantitative data, are often able to utilize the best aspects of each of these methods.

C. Intersectional Infrastructure Focused Research

Another knowledge gap relates to issues of exclusion. Despite planners' best intentions, some groups may be excluded from even large-scale public infrastructure projects due to complications brought on by inaccessibility. For example, pay structures may make some infrastructure unaffordable, construction features could render some buildings inaccessible for people with disabilities, delivery interruptions may make service provision unreliable, and insufficient enforcement of regulations may compromise safety. Inaccessibility may also arise due to the characteristics of infrastructure users. For example, people from marginalized castes, ethnicities, or low-income households may face social barriers in accessing and utilizing new infrastructure services. More work is needed on how men and women may be impacted differently by these issues of inaccessibility, and whether such disparities are magnified by issues of class, caste, and race/ethnicity.

D. Additional Work on Climate Change and ICT

Of the different types of infrastructure we reviewed in this study, there is the relatively less consensus on the gendered effects of access to ICT. Improving access to ICT services has the potential to close gender gaps in wage employment, income, time deficits, and financial

assets. In principle, the key mechanism is through an improvement in women's fallback positions and their bargaining power at home, which can contribute to a more equitable distribution of household work and/or the ability to pay for market substitutes. However, as we saw in this review, the evidence is mixed, and more work is needed on gendered effects of ICT infrastructure improvements.

A final suggestion we have for additional research relates to climate change. As particular regions continue to be ravaged by climate change, climate-aware infrastructure will become increasingly important. Current research has indicated that women in low-income countries are especially vulnerable to climate-change related costs and burdens, thus they should be at the table when climate-related infrastructures are being developed (Pearse 2017). Ultimately, new research at the intersection of ecofeminism and development economics is needed to better understand how can we use infrastructure to ensure women are not disproportionately harmed by climate change.

V. Policy Implications and Conclusion

This review has made clear that carefully developed physical and social infrastructure projects can improve gender equality and women's empowerment. An important question is thus how governments, development banks, the private sector, and public-private partnerships can most effectively facilitate such projects and oversee their success. Infrastructure planning and investment is complicated. For example, mismanagement issues and technical errors in the past have led major development banks that help fund such projects to institute new oversight policies and inspection processes (Bazbauers and Engel 2021). The OECD has also called for an integrated policy approach to sustainable infrastructure development with a gender lens, one that recognizes the gender-sustainable infrastructure nexus while at the same time navigating the

trade-offs that may occur between different goals and policies related to infrastructure development and gender equality (OECD 2019).

Adding assessments of gender inclusion and gendered impacts of infrastructure to oversight practices of infrastructure projects is critical. This is a necessary starting point for understanding how gender objectives of current and past projects can inform future projects. The World Bank (2010) provides six useful assessment criteria: (1) consultation (whether a public meeting was held with local women affected by the infrastructure project); (2) whether a gender analysis was conducted in the context of social or environmental assessments or resettlement action planning; (3) whether gender equality goals were listed as project development objectives; (4) gender-responsive design (e.g. in a transport project, were street lights and walkways included to make roads safer for women? Was there a gender quota implemented in hiring road construction workers?); (5) whether items in the budget were earmarked for targeted gender activities and designs; and (6) whether the project specifically monitored gender responsive indicators as the project progressed.

One example of an entry point to infuse gender into infrastructure projects based on public-private partnerships is to build incentives for gender inclusion into the contracts by requiring gender audits for their renewal (Waqar 2021). Private partners can be incentivized to consider gender in their projects by modeling such incentives after those regularly used to make private developers conform to SDG-related clauses in contracts (Owusu-Manu et al. 2020). Other mechanisms include tracking gender in satisfaction surveys; gender quotas and targets in recruitment; training, hiring, and provision of childcare for workers; and extending gender-related commitments into sub-contracts (PPPLRC 2022).

An additional policy recommendation to highlight is the importance of enhancing women's participation and voice in infrastructure planning, design, and execution. In this review we have highlighted some examples of infrastructure projects, especially in water supply, in which women's inclusion in project implementation contributed to measures of women's empowerment. Another example of a project that exemplifies best practices is including women in infrastructure planning is the campaign of Kerala, India to implement decentralized participatory planning and to stipulate mandatory gender-related expenditure minimums in local government budgets. The campaign resulted in greater community satisfaction levels with basic infrastructure development and maintenance (Heller et al. 2007). Additional examples of best practices in including women's voices in infrastructure development and planning are found in the UN-Habitat's online database of best practices (UN-Habitat 2023). Direct incentives for including women in project planning and development may thus help to improve not only women's empowerment but also the delivery of services and community organization. Other methods that help to both measure and enhance women's engagement in an infrastructure project include monitoring female participation during project meetings, building the capacity of women's groups, generating teams of women surveyors for data collection, and organizing separate public consultation meetings for men and women.

As made clear in our discussion of knowledge gaps, regular data collection and monitoring of gender inclusion of infrastructure projects is also recommended. Throughout this review, we have highlighted women's direct and indirect access to employment opportunities as a result of enhanced infrastructure investment. To best measure these direct employment effects, evaluators will need access to contractors' and subcontractors' employment records. Measuring indirect employment resulting from a development project is more challenging. Large-scale

projects, including those that improve access to water, ICT, transportation, or electricity for a large region or population, may use regression analysis based on large-scale household surveys, as well as time use analysis. However, smaller-scale projects, whose influence may not be captured in nationally representative quantitative data, should be accompanied by local surveys or qualitative research. Quantitative surveys may be preferred over qualitative ethnographies because they have the potential to be more widely representative and typically require fewer research resources. Additionally, randomized control trials imbedded in infrastructure projects can provide especially robust data for understanding the gendered effects of the project, but may be more difficult and costly to implement.

Much of the research on employment effects remains constrained by data availability and data quality. One issue is that women's labor market status is often measured by the female labor force participation rate, which is calculated from cross-sectional household surveys where the ILO definitions of labor force participation are employed to construct a binary indicator for employment. These definitions of labor force participation thus fail to capture labor conditions such as job security, job quality, worker vulnerability, adequacy of the remuneration, or more importantly, the trade-offs that women face. A second issue is the variation in survey instruments and definition of employment across countries, particularly in sectors where women are well-represented. The challenge of measuring this work leads to underreporting, undercounting and broad undervaluing of labor force participation and its role in the broader economy. A third issue is that labor force surveys seldom ask for detailed histories about an individual's labor force participation, job quality, and intermittency.

Of course, project-specific surveys, qualitative data, and large quantitative data can be used beyond trying to understand how infrastructure affects women's employment opportunities.

Researchers should also consider collecting and examining other metrics of gender equality and women's empowerment related to infrastructure projects. These measures include time spent in household production and in leisure activities (collected through time-use diaries), energy/transportation/ICT use by households and by gender, women's occupational segregation, women's decision-making power (collected through survey questions), gender-disaggregated data on earnings and health outcomes, and children's human capital accumulation. As illustrated in the studies highlighted in this review, these metrics are commonly used to assess gender equality and women's empowerment.

In closing, empowering women by incorporating gender dimensions into infrastructure planning and finance matters not only for individual well-being but also has important ramifications for investment in human capital, psychological and economic health, and overall development. Crucial are the implementation of public works programs that build and improve time-saving infrastructure (especially electrification and the access to clean water); and improvements in care infrastructure (especially the provision of on-site childcare facilities) that allow time poor individuals to engage in work in a meaningful manner. Indeed, the approaches to including gender objectives in infrastructure strategies and measuring the outcomes highlighted in this review are beneficial not only to women but also more broadly to all those whose well-being has been compromised by insufficient access to key infrastructures.

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Appendix 1.

In this appendix, we provide tables which summarize literature on gender empowerment and physical infrastructure.

Table 1. Literature on Electricity and Energy

Study	Area	Methods Used	Key Findings
Electricity and Energy			
Cecelski (2005)	Multiple countries	Descriptive statistics and correlation coefficients	Per capita energy consumption correlates closely with the Gender Development Index.
Rathi and Vermaak (2018)	India and South Africa	Propensity score matching and panel fixed effects estimation using survey data	Electrification raises the annual incomes earned by those who work in paid employment, for both men and women in both countries.
Samad and Zhang (2019)	India	Propensity-score-weighted fixed-effects regression model using survey data	Access to electricity increases not only women's employment, but also their freedom of movement and social participation.
Sedai, Nepal, and Jamasb (2021)	India	Panel fixed effects and instrumental variable regressions using survey data	Additional hours of electricity lead to better household outcomes.
Dinkelmann (2011)	South Africa	Panel fixed effects and instrumental variable regressions using survey data	The widescale roll-out of electricity to rural areas resulted in a 9 to 9.5 percentage point increase in women's employment, mostly because household electrification served as a labor-saving technology and reduced women's time spent in home production.
Grogan and Sadanand (2013)	Nicaragua	Probit regression analysis using survey data	Electricity is shown to increase the propensity of rural Nicaraguan women to work outside the home by about 23%, but to have no impact on male employment.
Fernández-Baldor, Boni, Lillo, and Hueso (2014)	Peru	Qualitative case study	Electrification of rural areas led to an increase in men's leisure time in the evenings while women spent more time sewing and knitting.
Sedai, Vasudevan, Pena, and Miller (2021)	India	Panel fixed effects and instrumental variable regressions using survey data	Reliable electrification improves the status of women through increased employment opportunities and reduced time allocation to home production.
Ferrant and Thim (2019)	Multiple countries	Descriptive statistics of time use data	Lack of electricity reliability, especially during peak periods, acts as an impediment to post-electrification decisions, such as the purchase of domestic appliances, which lowers the required time for home production and restricts the efficient allocation of women's time in home production and paid labor.
Atakhanova and Howie (2022)	Kazakhstan	OLS Regression and Descriptive Statistics using survey data	Women's representation among energy-sector managers has been falling over time, and this was worsened by COVID-19 and childcare deficits.
Kim and Standal (2019)	Kyrgyzstan	Qualitative interviews and observations	Lack of reliability and affordability of electricity in rural areas has undermined women's potential empowerment and has worked to maintain gender inequalities.
Standal and Winther (2016)	India and Afghanistan	Qualitative ethnographic case study	Electrification provided important resources and enhanced women's opportunities to perform their expected role as care workers more efficiently, and that many women appreciated this positive effect of electricity in their everyday lives.
Osummuyiwa and Ahlborg (2022)	Tanzania	Qualitative interviews and focus groups	The introduction of small-scale renewable energy systems meant that women entrepreneurs had more opportunities to expand their businesses. In addition, the new systems gave them more room to maneuver in daily life, and some shifts in gender norms followed.

Table 2. Water and Sanitation

Study	Area	Methods Used	Key Findings
Water and Sanitation			
Rost and Koissy-Kpein (2018)	Philippines, Uganda, and Zimbabwe	Descriptive statistics of household survey data	Access to an improved water source reduced women's average unpaid care workloads by one to four hours per day.
Hanrahan and Mercer (2019)	Canada	Focus group discussions and direct observation	Indigenous women reported that no piped water and limited access to potable water lengthened their workdays and undermined their physical and mental health.
Devoto et al. (2012)	Morocco	Randomized Control Trial	Among households who took up the access to the water grid, they experienced time gains which were used primarily for leisure and social activities and within six months, overall household well-being improved.
Kremer et al (2011)	Kenya	Randomized Control Trial	Investments in infrastructure to protect spring water led to less fecal contamination and a lower incidence of child diarrhea, which helps to reduce the time that women spend in unpaid labor activities.
Fletcher, Pande, and Moore (2017)	India	Descriptive statistics of survey data	Adult women spend 1–2 hours daily on average collecting and storing water, and studies have shown that time spent on water collection negatively affect both women's employment and personal health.
Sedai (2021)	India	Fixed-effects and instrumental variable regressions using survey data	A 0.1% increase in village access to indoor piped drinking water increases the likelihood of women's overall employment by 0.33 percentage points and women's wage/salary employment by 0.39 percentage points. Indoor piped drinking water improves health outcomes among women.
Parikh et al (2015)	India	Mixed methods, interviews and regression modeling	The provision of tap water and sanitation services (along with electrification and paved roads) has contributed to a substantial increase in education for women along with reduced health costs.
Winter, Darmstadt, and Davis (2021)	Zambia	Non-randomized, quasi-experimental design	Households that obtained piped water reduced their fetching time by 80%, with the majority of time saved accruing to women and girls.
Gins and Subramanian (2015)	India	Two-stage regression analysis using district-level data	Latrine availability in India is positively associated with women's labor force participation and women's literacy rates.
Koolwal and Van de Walle (2013)	Multiple countries	Regression analysis using household survey data	Lack of access to piped water in households with an increase in short-term morbidities (such as fever, cough, and diarrhea) and the inability to reallocate domestic chores that prevent children from attending school.
Baker, Story, Walsler-Kuntz, Zimmerman (2018)	India	Descriptive statistics of survey data	Water and sanitation access is also associated with improved birth weights.
Meeks (2017)	Kyrgyzstan	Regression analysis using household survey data	Access to clean water enhances labor and leisure time use.
Narain (2017)	India	Qualitative semi-structured interviews, direct observation, and participatory rural appraisal tools	Men's expectations of water use changed when infrastructure interventions brought piped water to the region. Piped water reduced the distance women walked to reach water sources, but there was an increase in the volume of water women were expected to carry.
Irianti and Prasetyoputra (2019)	Indonesia	Multivariable logistic regression analysis using survey data	Households with piped water are more likely to rely on women to fetch additional water compared to those without piped water.
Thara (2017)	India	Qualitative interviews	Women acknowledged that piped water might save time and increase mobility, but retorted that the requirement to pay for the water outweighed the benefits of piped water.
Shrestha, Chapagain, and Ghimire (2019)	Nepal	Mixed methods: quantitative administrative data, field observations, surveys, focus groups and interviews	A decrease in water volume and changes in the geography of water sources led to increased water stress borne by women.
Were, Roy, and Swallow (2008)	Kenya	Mixed methods: primary survey collection and focus groups	Community organization around water supply improved when women were included in having responsibility for water management.
Leino (2007)	Kenya	Randomized intervention and regression analysis	No evidence that increases in women's participation in water user committees altered other outcomes in the community, but gender inclusion in water management can be a useful way to boost women's empowerment without distorting delivery of public goods.
Grant, Soeters, Bunthocun, and Willetts (2019)	Cambodia	Qualitative structured interviews	Women's ownership and management of water supply infrastructures led to improvements in women's empowerment, but that they were constrained by domestic obligations.
Leite (2010)	Brazil	Case studies	The integration of gender perspectives in water distribution systems can improve women's access to safe water and adequate sanitation.

Table 3. Transportation

Study	Area	Methods Used	Key Findings
Transportation			
Porter (2008)	Sub-Saharan African countries	Literature review	Men tend to be the principal operators and owners of commercial motorized and non-motorized transport, while women are commonly pedestrian transporters.
Adeel, Yeh, Zhang (2017)	Pakistan	Regression analysis using time use data	Men account for about 80% of all trips and are more likely than women to use motorized transportation for these trips.
Njenga and Tanzani (2020)	Ghana, Uganda, Kenya and Tanzania	Qualitative interviews and case study	Women frequently travel with dependents and because they have less access to vehicular travel than men, they often walk further and rely upon more basic infrastructure such as footpaths and trail bridges to complete household chores.
Orkoh, Blaauw, and Claassen (2020)	Ghana	Regression analysis using household survey data	Traffic congestion in urban areas contributes to time poverty rates that are higher for women than men. Investment in the public transportation infrastructure can reduce the spent stuck in traffic and help to reduce time poverty.
Lei, Desai, and Vanneman (2019)	India	Fixed-effect regression using survey data	Paved roads, unpaved roads, and frequent bus services increase the odds of non-agricultural employment among both men and women, but the effect is stronger among women.
Seki and Yamada (2020)	India	Difference-in-differences model	Proximity to the Delhi Metro stations significantly increases the female employment rate, whereas its effect on men's employment is ambiguous.
Martinez et al (2020)	Peru	Difference-in-differences model	Investments and improvements in urban transport systems can improve women's employment outcomes.
Brooks and Donovan (2020)	Nicaragua	Regression analysis using household survey data	New rural trail bridges result in a 60% increase in women entering the labor market.
Ouko, Gachari, Sichangi, and Alegana (2019)	Kenya	Mixed methods, geographic information system (GIS) analysis and semi-structured interviews	poor geographic access to healthcare providers is the single biggest contributor to maternal mortality rates in Siaya County, Kenya.
Sacks et al (2016)	Zambia and Uganda	Mixed methods, interviews and surveys	For mothers who deliver at home, lack of affordability, accessibility, and adequacy in transportation options helped to explain why they did not travel to the health facility.
Assoumou Ella (2021)	Belgium	VAR Granger Causality Modeling	Women use public transportation more often than men to travel for work and family reasons, and they were therefore more likely to be exposed to COVID-19.
Onishi (2017)	India	Qualitative interviews	the introduction of Delhi Metro is shown to have drastically changed transportation choices for women, due to the high safety standard in the Metro system.
Borker (2021)	India	Random utility framework: using survey, mapping, and crowd-sourced mobile application safety data	Women are willing to choose a college in the bottom half of the quality distribution over a college in the top quintile in order to travel by a safer route.
Garrard, Rose, and Lo (2008)	Australia	Quantitative observation data	Women commuter cyclists prefer to use routes with maximum separation from motorized traffic while men are more willing to bike closer to traffic.
Dinkelmann and Ngai (2022)	African countries	Descriptive statistics	Some countries have begun to implement transportation policies and provide facilities that allow men and women to travel separately.
Aguilar, Gutiérrez, and Villagrán (2021)	Mexico	Regression discontinuity design using survey data	Mexico City's "women traveling safely program," which includes women-only subway cars, has resulted lower rates of sexual harassment against women riders during the times when this option was available.
Kondylis et al (2020)	Brazil	Implicit Association Tests	Safe space reserved for women on the suburban rail system reduces the rate of physical harassment by 50%.
Salon and Gulyani (2010)	Kenya	Joint-choice modelling using survey data	Low income individuals cannot afford any of the motorized transport options in the city. People cope by limiting their travel outside their settlement and, if they do travel, it is often by walking. They also find that women and children disproportionately bear the burden of reduced mobility.
Winstlott Hiselius et al (2019)	Sweden	Regression analysis	Women's presence in local policymaking leads to more environmentally sustainable transportation policies.
Kaiser and Barstow (2022)	Multiple countries	Literature review	Women's inclusion is important for the expression of specific needs in infrastructural planning and implementation processes.

Table 4. Information and Communication Technology

Study	Area	Methods Used	Key Findings
Information and Communication Technology			
Venkatesh et al. (2017)	India	Quasi-experimental analysis	The highest levels of entrepreneurial activity are observed among women with high ICT use.
Crittenden, Crittenden, and Ajjan (2019)	South Africa	Structural equation modeling using survey data	ICT usage decisions among women entrepreneurs were influenced by women's perceptions of ICT ease of use and usefulness.
Mumporeze and Prierer (2017)	Rwanda	Qualitative interviews	Heavy domestic responsibilities and computer anxiety keep women from using ICT at higher rates.
Ávila and Abad (2019)	Peru	Qualitative interviews	Improvements in access to ICT have increased women's access to education.
Laizu, Arnarego, and Sudweeks (2010)	Bangladesh	Mixed methods: interviews and questionnaires	Domestic control of ICT resources affects women's sense of independence, freedom, and self-esteem.
Handapangoda and Kumara (2013)	Sri Lanka	Ethnographic surveys	Women's access to mobile phones strengthened and expanded their support networks and opened them up to newer activities. Effects were dampened when the phones were not owned by the women themselves and instead controlled by their husbands.
Suri and Jack (2016)	Kenya	Individual and household level regressions	The spread of ICT services has also facilitated innovations in financial technology, mobile financial services, and mobile money, which have helped to promote poverty reduction and income redistribution in a number of countries.
Wyche and Olson (2018)	Kenya	Observations and group interviews	Women tend to have secondhand cell phones which are often broken, face heavy time constraints of unpaid work, and face misinformation about social media which inhibits their ability to effectively use ICT.
Primo and Khan (2003)	Multiple countries	Literature review	Men are free to walk long distances (during the day or night) to seek Internet cafes, while women must focus on home chores or are unable to walk at night.
Gillwald, Milek, and Stork (2010)	African countries	Descriptive statistics and regression analysis using survey data	Women cited cost as the main reason they were not connected to the Internet.
Asiedu et al (2013)	Sub-Saharan African countries	Ordered probit regression model using enterprise data	Female-owned firms are more credit constrained in sub-Saharan Africa than male-owned.
Menon and Rodgers (2011)	India	IV Regression using survey data	Access to credit encourages women's self-employment.
Nwosu and Orji (2017)	Nigeria	Propensity score matching regressions using enterprise data	Access to formal credit improves women entrepreneur's likelihood of successful enterprise performance.
Demirgüç-Kunt et al (2013)	Multiple countries	Regression analysis using survey data	Women's access to banking is closely related to country-level restrictions on women's work, violence against women, and early age marriage.
Morsy (2020)	Multiple countries	Regression analysis using survey data	Women are more likely to be excluded from the financial sector in countries where credit information is less available through public and private credit registries and where gaps between women and men in educational attainment are large.
Glavec-Geo et al (2017)	Pakistan	Mixed methods: interviews and descriptive statistics	Significant differences between men and women on adoption of mobile banking are driven by social norms.
Riquelme and Rios (2010)	Singapore	Descriptive statistics	Social norms affect women's intention to adopt internet banking.
Tsai (2000)	China	Historical analysis	Women often make use of rotating savings and credit associations (ROSCAs) to fill gendered gaps in financing needs.
Anderson and Baland (2002)	Kenya	Regression analysis using household survey data	Most women use ROSCAs to protect their savings against claims made by their husbands for immediate consumption.
Sedai, Vasudevan, and Pena (2021)	India	IV Regression using survey data	Women's ROSCA membership improves their decision-making power in households as well as their fertility choice making.
Chen et al (2016)	China	Regression analysis using administrative data	Female borrowers pay higher interest rates even though default rates of loans from female borrowers are significantly lower than those from male borrowers.

Appendix 2.

In this appendix, we provide tables which summarize literature on gender empowerment and social infrastructure.

Table 5. Education

Study	Area	Methods Used	Key Findings
Education			
Chicoine (2021)	Ethiopia	Difference-in-differences model using survey data	The removal of school fees led to an increase in schooling for women, and that each additional year of schooling led to a reduction in fertility.
Zenebe Gebre (2019)	Malawi	Difference-in-differences model using survey data	The introduction of free primary education led to reductions in fertility.
Putra, Dendup, and Januraga (2021)	Indonesia	Logistic regression models using survey data	Women's sense of confidence in asking her husband to use a condom improved with higher levels of education.
Eze-Ajoku et al., (2022)	Nigeria	Regression models using survey data	Women with higher levels of education are less tolerant of spousal physical violence.
Hosein (2019)	Trinidad and Tobago	Logistic regression models using survey data	Women's increased empowerment, especially in terms of higher levels of education, can trigger a backlash effect among men, putting women at even higher risks of domestic violence.
Hossain and Tisdell (2005)	Bangladesh	Descriptive statistics and regression analysis	Women's educational attainment is positively associated with their workforce participation.
Shah (2007)	Pakistan	OLS regression using primary survey data	Higher education enhances the earning of women teaching at public sector educational institutions.
Le and Nguyen (2021)	Multiple countries	Regression analysis	Education is positively associated with women's intrahousehold decision making authority.
Chatterjee, Desai, and Vanneman (2018)	India	Regression analysis using survey data	Women's education and labor force participation have a U-shaped relationship: the income effect accounts for some of the U-shape and a lack of suitable employment opportunities also contributes.
Ojobo (2008)	Nigeria	Mixed methods: qualitative interviews and descriptive statistics	Economic constraints, religious constraints, unpaid domestic responsibilities, unequal employment opportunities, and early marriage are largely responsible for gender differences in educational attainment.
Jacoby and Mansuri (2011)	Pakistan	Mixed methods: qualitative interviews and regression analysis	Optimal placement of new schools needs to take into account social restrictions on mobility that girls may face.
Muralidharan and Sheth (2016)	India	Regression analysis using administrative data	Recruiting and retaining female teachers is effective at reducing gender gaps in rural children's education.

Table 6. Healthcare

Study	Area	Methods Used	Key Findings
Healthcare			
Osundina (2020)	Nigeria	Regression analysis using survey data	Positive relationship between the health status of women and their labor force participation
Sreenu (2019)	India	Mixed methods, primary quantitative and qualitative surveys	Healthcare facilities are in poor condition and that due to geographic constraints, many community members turn to more expensive, private care to meet their needs.
Williamson et al. (2009).	Multiple countries	Literature review	Young women who want contraceptives and healthcare often cannot get these services because of the long distance
Chib (2010)	Indonesia	RCT, qualitative interviews	Mobile phones facilitate smoother communication and allow speedier emergency response for midwives. Phones also helped them gather and disseminate health-related information to the patient community.
Ganle et al. (2016)	Ghana	Qualitative interviews	Women with disabilities reported that most healthcare facilities currently lack ramps, wheelchairs, and disability-friendly delivery beds.

Table 7. Social Care Services

Study	Area	Methods Used	Key Findings
Social Care Services			
Kawabata (2014)	Japan	Regression analysis using primary survey and geospatial data	Access to childcare is closely associated with a higher probability of attaining preferred employment among women with preschool-aged children.
Sinha and Sedai (2022)	Nepal	IV regression using survey data	Unpaid care work within households can negatively affect care providers' well-being outcomes, which has adverse consequences for the macroeconomy and human development outcomes
Folbre (2014)	Multiple African countries	Literature review	Women work significantly longer hours than men overall and bear a disproportionate share of the direct and indirect costs of caring for dependents.
Barros et al. (2013)	Brazil	RCT	Access to free child care leads to an increase in the use of care and mothers' employment and income.
Hallman et al. (2005)	Guatemala	Regression analysis using primary survey data	Reductions in care prices and in travel time to care providers have a large positive effect on low-income women's paid labor hours.
Clark et al. (2019)	Nairobi	RCT	Women who were offered vouchers for subsidized childcare were 8.5 percentage points more likely to be employed than those who were not given vouchers.
Moussié (2021)	Multiple countries	Literature review	Childcare centers are often not near areas where informal workers work.
Mahal and McPake (2017)	Multiple Asian countries	Literature review	Progress on public eldercare provisions has remained uneven depending on the size of public sector health budgets.
Rodgers and Zveglich (2021)	Multiple Asian countries	Regression analysis using survey data	Gender differences in seeking care treatments vary by gender and age.
Stark (2005)	Multiple European countries	Literature review	Women's unpaid labor is often relied upon to care for older family members.
Yoon (2014)	Republic of Korea	Descriptive statistics using survey data	Unpaid care for older men is often provided by spouses, while for women it is provided by other family members, especially by daughters.
Chen et al (2018)	China	Regression analysis using survey data	Older women are more likely to have unmet care needs. Unpaid care for older men is often provided by spouses, while for women it is provided by other family members, especially by daughters.
Stark and Cukrowska-Torzewska (2018)	Multiple European countries	Regression analysis using survey data	Unpaid care for older men is often provided by spouses, while for women it is provided by other family members, especially by daughters.